

**STUDYING THE CONSUMERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS BUYING CLOTHES IN GEORGIA
THROUGH THE EXAMPLE OF THE IMERETI REGION**

Karkashadze N.,

*Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration,
Akaki Tsereteli State University
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1870-0502>*

Kutaisi, Georgi

Benidze N.,

*Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration,
Akaki Tsereteli State University,
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9070-8219>*

Kutaisi, Georgia

Ukleba Sh.

*Visiting teacher, Department of Business Administration,
Akaki Tsereteli State University
Kutaisi, Georgia*

Abstract

The main attention in the article is paid to the importance of clothes in the daily lives of consumers. It also tells about the factors and situations affecting the process of buying clothes. And finally, the analysis of the survey results is presented, from which it is clear what consumers prefer when buying clothes and why online shopping and traditional stores are important. In addition, conclusions were drawn and recommendations were given, which will help companies attract consumers and increase their loyalty.

Keywords: consumer; purchasing process; funding function.

In a modern market economy, companies need to understand how people choose to purchase goods that are an integral part of their lives, particularly clothes, which can be attributed to items of daily use, as well as goods of special and rare demand. With time, along with changes in fashion, trends, and technology development, people's needs, interests, and tastes change, which we think is first of all reflected in their clothes. Nowadays, clothing is not just a necessary commodity; it has found a greater interest, especially for people concerned with certain factors, such as brands, fashion, originality, and so on.

In the book *Consumer Behavior*, Blackwell, Miniard, and Engel state: "To succeed in a hypercompetitive future, firms of all sizes and types must focus their attention on a core aspect of business operations, namely understanding how consumers make purchasing decisions". In order to formulate a strategy for retaining existing customers and attracting new ones, both commercial and non-commercial organizations must analyze and understand the trends of the end users' thoughts regarding the goods and services offered. If it is clear why consumers buy these particular goods and no others, how they will buy them, what their lifestyle is, and how demographic, psychographic, and environmental factors affect their choice, then the sellers can determine a means of satisfying the needs and desires of consumers, which may require the creation of new goods or the disappearance of old ones from the shelves [1].

However, the way consumers make purchasing decisions about clothing depends on cultural, ethnic, and motivational variables, which increases the demand for consumer analysts and researchers.

In general, the purchasing process is complex and includes a variety of stages. First of all, it is necessary

to find out why or for what reason people buy clothing, where they prefer to buy it, and which payment method is acceptable for them.

The surveys on these issues have been interesting for companies in every era, and even today, these surveys are still being conducted in connection with this, because, along with the development of humanity, they have also changed. Therefore, surveys conducted over the years have led to the development of many theories and models of consumer buying behavior. One of them is a survey that we conducted, which will help us make a certain outline and develop appropriate recommendations on the process of buying clothes and the contributing factors.

The process of buying clothes is different for everyone because everyone has different life experiences, tastes, and perceptions. However, there is something that is unique to each person, which is reflected in the motivation, which is why the behaviors are also specific for everyone. Here are 5 reasons that influence our choices: the need to stand out amongst others, to belong to something, to look like celebrities, or concern for social reasons.

For the survey on this issue, we chose as the target audience the students and teaching staff of ATSU, whose ages ranged from 17 to 70. 70% of them are females.

The survey showed that 63.6% of respondents buy clothes as they wish, 60% as needed, 9.1% for creating new collections, and 12.7% - due to discounts.

It was also important to know what consumers prefer when choosing clothes. As it became clear from the surveys, first of all, comfort in wear is important for 76.4%, quality – for 63.6%, price – for 56.4%, and then there are factors such as brand, originality, visual, etc.

As you know, the buying process does not involve making a decision that can be changed for various reasons. It was just important to find out what factors can change the consumer's mind about buying. The survey showed that, according to the respondents, abstention from buying is mainly caused by the absence/lack of money - 63%, as well as rudeness and inattention on the part of service personnel - 24%, and non-branded goods - 13% (see Diagram 1).

It should be noted that the developments in recent years, which are mainly related to the pandemic, have made some changes in the purchasing process, which is manifested in the fact that online shopping has increased significantly. Therefore, it was important for us to find out what role online shopping plays when buying clothes. The conducted surveys showed the following: online shopping is preferred by 16.4%, traditional store by 45.5% and both are preferred by 38.2% (see Diagram 2).

Diagram 1.

Diagram 2.

Although there are not so many supporters of online stores, it is still necessary to know why online trading is important to them. As a result of the survey, the answers of the respondents were as follows: (see Diagram 3).

Diagram 3.

It is also interesting to see which online stores and sites are taking advantage of consumer benefits. From the survey, it was found that if they choose online shopping, they prefer the online shops Trendyol (60%) and Zara (56.7%), and they choose them because they have a wider choice of products.

Diagram 4.

As for a traditional store, the proportions of respondents replying were as follows: 50% choose the market-places, followed by fashion stores such as Cotton (32.5%), Defacto and Waikiki (27.5%), and the second-hand stores (22.5%). Generally speaking, 89% of consumers choose traditional stores because it is important for them to see the goods with their own eyes and try on them before buying.

Diagram 5

As for those audience members who chose both options, they use online when they couldn't find what they wanted in the store (76.5%), when there are discounts (44.1%), when they don't have time (32.4%), and they go to a traditional store when they don't know exactly what they want (78.8%), to relax (24.2%), when they have time (12.1%).

Based on the results of the conducted surveys, the following conclusions can be drawn:

➤ Despite the fact that most of the respondents buy clothes according to their desire and need, it is necessary to pay no less attention to the part of consumers who buy clothes as a gift, during discounts, or for a new collection.

➤ In addition to the fact that when trying on clothing, consumers give preference to its quality and appearance, it is also very important for the seller to focus on the originality and branding of the goods offered.

➤ It is also important to pay attention to the personal qualities of the salespersons, because they are the ones who will turn the consumer into a regular customer due to their professional and pleasant approach to the client.

➤ Although most consumers do their shopping online because of a wider choice of products, it is unacceptable to offer consumers so many choices that

they find it difficult to choose the products that are acceptable to them. The main thing is not a lot of goods, but in such a quantity that it is not difficult for consumers to make a choice, as well as the goods that they want and prefer.

➤ As the study showed, the issue of financial security for consumers is often an obstacle to purchasing clothes, and not only clothes, therefore, from this point of view, sellers should pay greater attention to the use of the marketing funding function, which will increase consumer loyalty to the seller.

➤ Finally, it should be noted that the tastes and opinions of consumers change rapidly, so the process of studying their opinions should be conducted continuously.

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